

DURABILITY STUDIES OF NANOPHASED FRP COMPOSITES UNDER SYNERGISTIC EXPOSURE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced composite laminates are often used in harsh environments that may affect their long-term durability and life. In general, environmental degradation is observed as matrix cracking and swelling due to water sorption that leads to interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix. In this work, first matrix properties were modified using 1- 2 wt.% of nanoclay and then composite laminates were fabricated using vacuum assisted resin infusion molding (VARIM) process. Unidirectional E- glass fibers and SC-15 epoxy resin were used along with Nanomer I. 28E nanoclay. Neat and nanophased composites were subjected to different environmental conditioning i.e. elevated temperature (dry, wet: 60°C and 80°C) and cold (dry, wet: -18°C) for 15, 45 and 90 days. In addition, samples were exposed to ultraviolet radiation (UV) and/or condensation (UC) for 5, 10 and 15 days. The percentage weight gain due to water absorption and humid conditions was calculated. Micrographic analysis and quasi-static flexure tests were performed on the conditioned samples. Additionally, room temperature conditioned samples were also tested to consider as baseline. Samples subjected to hot-wet conditions showed higher percentage weight gain. Experimental results show degradation in mechanical properties with increasing time. Greater effects of degradation were observed for hot- wet (80°C) samples. However, less degradation in nanophased composites was noticed over neat composites. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) results of failed wet conditioned samples show better interfacial bonding in nanophased composites in comparison to neat samples similarly conditioned.

Keywords: E-glass/epoxy composite; elevated temperature; subzero; UV radiation/condensation

INTRODUCTION

Composites are known for their strength- weight ratio, corrosion resistance and superior fatigue performances compared to metallic materials and hence are the ideal materials for consideration in the many applications [1-2]. Unfortunately the downside of polymeric composites is their inherent viscoelastic behavior. Microstructural changes, time-dependent deformation, degradation in mechanical properties are identified in FRP composites when exposed to environmental conditions such as heat and moisture [3-4]. Sander reported degradation in mechanical properties, cracking and

flaking of polymers exposed to elevated temperatures [5]. Ellyin and Maser investigated the effects of moisture absorption and exposure to elevated temperature on the mechanical properties of glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) tubes and observed water damage at the glass fiber interphase with increasing water temperature [6]. Water that diffuses into the composites ends up either in the matrix or at the interphase region. Thus the amount of moisture absorbed by the matrix resin is significantly different than that by the reinforcement fiber. This results in a mismatch in moisture induced volumetric expansion between the matrix and the fibers, and thus leads to the evolution of localized stress and strain fields in composites [7-8]. Plasticization, swelling stress, hydrolysis and formation of cracks are the possible occurrences of environmental exposure which should also influence the diffusion of water in the composites [9-10]. Preconditioning in elevated temperature in water ($> 75^{\circ}\text{C}$) always has a deleterious effect on the GFRP [11-13]. Polymer composites in outdoor applications are also exposed to ultraviolet radiation and are susceptible to photo-initiated oxidation leading to surface degradation [14-15]. The durability of polymer composites in such an environment is one of the primary issues limiting the acceptance of these materials in many applications especially in infrastructural applications.

Recent advancement in modifying the matrix properties with the addition of small weight percentage of nanoparticle has shown significant improvement in strength and durability of both the matrix and FRP composites. Inorganic nanoparticles have gained acceptance as potential reinforcing materials because of their low cost and ease of fabrication [16-17]. Many researchers attempted to enhance properties of different types of polymers by the addition of nanoclays. Addition of nanoclay increases the barrier properties and enhances interfacial bonding [18]. Ricky et al. [19] investigated environmental degradation of epoxy nanocomposites due to UV exposure. They reported thicker and shallower cracks with less degree of discoloration in epoxy nanocomposites over neat counterparts. They credited the reason to the excellent barrier characteristics of organoclay with high aspect ratio. Similar results were also reported by Nanocor Inc. [18]. Hackman and Hollaway studied the potential applications of clay nanocomposite materials to civil engineering structures. They concluded that their ability to increase service life of materials subjected to aggressive environments could be utilized to increase the durability of glass and carbon fiber composites [20]. The objective of the work reported here is to utilize the advantages of nanoclay mentioned above by modifying the matrix and to study the durability of polymer composites following exposure to individual and synergistic environmental conditions.

MATERIALS AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

SC-15 epoxy resin, Nanomer I-28 E nanoclay and unidirectional E-glass fibers are used in this study. 1-2 wt.% nanoclay was dispersed in part A of SC-15 epoxy resin with a magnetic stirrer for 2 hours. The modified part A was then mixed with part B of SC-15 epoxy at a ratio of 10:3 using a high speed mechanical stirrer for 5 minutes and degassed for 30 minutes. Vacuum assisted resin infusion molding (VARIM) process was then used for fabricating E-glass/epoxy composites. The fiber volume fraction of these composites was determined using ASTM standards and found to be between 52-54%.

ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONING

Samples were exposed to four different conditions. These were: cold (subzero: dry, CD) cold (subzero: wet, CW), hot (elevated temperature: dry, HD), and hot (elevated temperature: wet, HW). For subzero dry/ wet conditioning, the samples were put in a box with/ without water and then was placed in a deep freezer. For hot-dry conditioning, the samples were placed in convection ovens maintained at elevated temperatures of 60° and 80°C. For hot-wet conditioning, the samples were placed in a hot water bath maintained at two elevated temperatures of 60° and 80°C. Other set of samples were exposed to two different conditions: Exposure to Ultraviolet radiation (UV) only and sequential exposure to UV radiation followed by condensation (UC). Under each condition, specimens were exposed to 120 (five days), 240 (ten days) and 360 hrs (15 days). In addition, room temperature (RT) conditioned samples (neat, 1% and 2%) were used to generate base line data.

EXPERIMENTAL

Weight gain analysis

The samples were weighed with a Mettler AT250 digital balance (precision 0.01 mg). The percent weight gain as function of time was calculated using equation 1:

$$\% \text{ Weight gain} = \frac{w_f - w_i}{w_f} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where w_f is the final weight of the sample and w_i is the initial weight of the dry sample at room temperature.

Flexural test

A minimum of five samples of each set were used for all the tests. Quasi- static flexure tests were carried out using Zwick – Roell testing machine to obtain flexure properties. Span length of the samples was 80 mm and the nominal thickness was 5 mm, while the width was maintained at 12.5 mm. Tests were conducted in displacement control mode with crosshead speed of 1.2 mm/min. Load-deflection data for each sample was collected. Flexural modulus was calculated from the slope of stress-strain plot. The maximum stress at failure on the tension side of a flexural specimen is considered the flexural strength of the material. Thus, using the homogeneous beam theory, the flexural strength in a three-point flexural test is found by using equation 2

$$\sigma_{UF} = \frac{3P_{\max}L}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

Where P_{max} =Maximum load at failure, b = Specimen width, d=Specimen thickness, L=Specimen length between the two support points

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Weight gain analysis

Hot and sub-zero conditioning

The average weight increase in each sample due to water absorption is shown in Fig. 1. As the material is submerged in distilled water, the amount of its moisture absorption depends on the duration and temperature of the water as shown in Fig. 1 with the maximum absorption occurring at higher temperature.

Fig. 1. Percentage increase in weight of neat/ nano GFRP conditioned samples.

The change in conditioning environment from room temperature to 80°C hot-wet for 90 days resulted in 3.5% increase in moisture absorption in neat GFRP composites samples and 2.4% in 2wt% GFRP composites samples as shown in this figure. This decrease in weight gain may be attributed to the enhancement in barrier properties of polymer matrix by the addition of nanoclay particle [18-19]. For hot-dry conditioned samples, initially increase in weight gain was observed but decreases afterwards. Usually, high temperature may act as activator for desorption phenomena. The very fast drying, generation and regeneration of residual stresses may quite often induce matrix as well as interfacial cracking. These microcracks in turn provide fast desorption paths for absorbed moisture. Weight gain in cold condition may due to the increase in swelling stresses, due to the volume expansion of moisture during freezing.

Ultraviolet radiation and/or condensation conditioning

Figure 2 shows the weight gain/loss (%) vs. number of days of neat, 1 wt. % and 2 wt. % specimens exposed to UV and/or condensation conditions. Phelps et al. [21] reported that thermal energy was sufficient to break bonds in cured epoxy, the

temperature in QUV chamber was maintained at 50°C. Also, in order to have the pure irradiation effect on the samples, an irradiation of 4 X 0.68 W/m² was used. Specimens exposed to UV conditions showed loss in weight with respect to time as shown in Fig. 2. But, after 9 days (216 hours), loss in weight reached a saturation point and showed no further decrease with respect to time. In polymers, chain – scission will produce small molecules when exposed to UV radiation. These small molecules are capped by oxygen from air free to migrate out from the specimen, causing weight loss. Since most of the polymer has less resistance to radiation, it is also possible that oxygen can easily diffuse into the specimen from air and accelerate the degradation of matrix.

Specimens exposed to cyclic ultraviolet radiation and condensation showed gain in weight with respect to time with a maximum of 1.2 % in neat and 0.8% in 2 wt.% samples after 15 days conditioning. However, water absorption reached saturation level in both condensation and UV+ condensation samples and showed no further gain with respect to time after approximately 9 days of conditioning. The increase in weight gain in condensation condition can be attributed to conjunct effect of UV radiation and moisture. Ultraviolet irradiation produces microcracks on the surface and provides pathway for rapid ingress of moisture. Also, the presence of moisture may enhance photo- oxidation reactions resulting in chain scission. Water vapor, especially in form of condensation can also remove soluble products of photo- oxidation reactions from a UV irradiated surface and thereby expose fresh surfaces susceptible to further degradation by UV radiation. However, 2 wt.% nanoclay infused composites showed less effect of both UV radiation and/or condensation. The loss in weight UV radiation and weight gain in UV+ condensation are significantly reduced in comparison to neat and 1 wt.% loaded samples. This can be attributed to the gas/moisture and radiation barrier properties of montmorillonite nanoclay which is consistent with results reported by Ricky et al. [19]. Also, addition of nanoclay might have increased the surface interaction with polymers. Due to this enhancement in crosslinking of polymer chains, effect of environmental conditions may be subsidized / retarded and thereby improves the overall performance.

Fig. 2. Change in sample weight as a function of time exposed to UV radiation and condensation.

Flexural test results: Samples exposed to hot and sub-zero conditioning

Flexural stress- strain response and their property variation with nanoclay addition with respect to time and conditions are given in Fig. 3 and Table 1. The general trend observed is of decreasing strength, strain and modulus with a maximum decrease in wet conditioned samples. At room temperature conditioning, 2 wt.% nanophased samples showed 60% and 31% increase in strength and modulus over neat samples. Degradation is observed in all the conditioned samples irrespective of the loading in comparison to room temperature conditioned samples. The maximum degradation is observed in hot-wet 90 days condition samples, 21% and 39% in neat composite, 22% and 40% in 1 wt.% composite, and 45% and 30% in 2 wt.% composites, respectively. However, 2 wt.% GFRP composites samples showed significant enhancement in properties in comparison to neat composites samples in all the set conditions. The decrease in properties can be attributed to the weight gain due to moisture absorption. The water overtime may diffuse into the composites saturating the matrix and may even reach the fiber/matrix interface. Since the resin used in this work is epoxy that has optimum chances of absorbing water as the organic groups in the backbone of epoxy have favorable interaction with water. This results in plasticization of matrix creating free volume and thus decreases the properties. The presence of water at the interface region may relieve the residual stresses that are generated during fabrication. Elevated temperature conditions couple with water may further strengthen the degradation process by creating cracks in the matrix and decreasing the bonding. Enhancement in nanophased composites can be attributed to the catalytic effect of nanoclay which increases the crosslinking between polymer chain, increases the cross linking density. Due to this enhancement in crosslinking of polymer chains, effect of environmental conditions may be subsidized and thus improves the overall performance. Similar behavior was observed in 15 and 45 days conditioned samples. The degradation rate was higher initially upto 15 days of conditioning and thereafter nominal degradation was observed in all the set samples.

Fig. 3. Flexural strength and modulus of neat/ nano GFRP conditioned samples.

Table 1. Percentage increase in flexural properties of neat/ nano GFRP composites over neat composites, similarly conditioned.

Percentage increase in strength/modulus of 1 wt.% samples over neat samples				Percentage increase in strength/modulus of 2 wt.% samples over neat samples		
Condition	15days	45days	90days	15days	45days	90days
RT		+8/+3			+19/+13	
hd:60°C	+8/+8.5	+6/+11	+6.6/+7	+21/+20	+34/+15.7	+35/+17
hw 60°C	+16/-10	+9/+1.5	+8/+5	+23/+5.5	+30/+14	+27.5/+17
hd: 80°C	+9/+10	+5/+9.8	+7/+12	+26/+11	+29.7/+4.4	+32/+8.7
hw: 80°C	+4/+1.6	+5/+3.3	+4/+3	+28/16	+26.4/+18	+22/+15
cd: -18°C	+7/-0.3	+14/-1.2	+15/-3	+12/+10	+29/+2.8	+36/+2.4
cw: -18°C	+18/-3.2	+9/ -0.2	+5/+4.3	+25/+1	+30.7/+0.7	+31/+9.4

Flexural test results: Samples exposed to UV radiation and/or condensation conditioning

Here also the general trend observed was of decreasing strength and modulus with a maximum decrease in ultraviolet irradiated + condensation (UC) conditioned samples shown in Fig. 4. At room temperature conditioning, 2 wt.% nanophased samples showed 19% and 13% increase in strength and modulus over neat samples. Degradation was observed in all the conditioned samples irrespective of the loading. The maximum degradation was observed in UC 90 days conditioned samples as shown in Table 2. However, 2 wt.% GFRP composite samples showed significant enhancement in properties in comparison to neat composite samples in all the set conditions.

Fig. 4. Flexural stress- strain response of ultraviolet radiation and/or condensation conditioned Samples.

Table 2. Flexural Properties of ultraviolet radiation and/or condensation conditioned neat and nanophased samples.

Flexural Strength (MPa)						
Condition	5days	% Change wrt. To RT	10days	% Change wrt. To RT	15days	% Change wrt. To RT
Neat RT	738.3±3.6	x	738.3±3.6	x	738.3±3.6	x
Neat UV	710±5.7	-4	690±3.7	-7	675.17±5.2	-9.4
Neat UC	683.15±7.2	-8.1	657±6.3	-12.4	601.41±3.2	-22.7
1% RT	798±2.6	x	798±2.6	x	798±2.6	x
1% UV	744.9±7.34	-7	710.34±3.5	-12.3	663.52±6.3	-20.3
1% UC	707.2±	-12.8	690±3.2	-15.7	649.15±2.7	-23
2% RT	878.2±1.8	x	878.2±1.8	x	878.2±1.8	x
2% UV	820±6.2	-7.1	753±3.5	-16.6	747±4.6	-17.7
2% UC	785.4±3.7	-11.8	725.28±6.3	-21.1	720.4±2.9	-22

Flexural Modulus (GPa)						
Condition	5days	% Change wrt. To RT	10days	% Change wrt. To RT	15days	% Change wrt. To RT
Neat RT	35±1	x	35±1	x	35±1	x
Neat UV	34.5±0.7	-1.5	34±1.1	-2.9	31.77±1.5	-10.2
Neat UC	34.7±1.4	-0.9	32.2±0.2	-8.7	32±0.6	-9.4
1% RT	35.37±0.5	x	35.37±0.5	x	35.37±0.5	x
1% UV	34.21±0.7	-3.2	33.8±1.0	-4.4	32.29±0.7	-9
1% UC	34.7±0.6	-1.8	34±0.35	-3.8	32±0.4	-10.3
2% RT	38.7±1.7	x	38.7±1.7	x	38.7±1.7	x
2% UV	37.39±1.4	-3.5	36±0.5	-7.5	35.05±0.7	-10.4
2% UC	36.84±0.5	-5	34.3±1.3	-12.8	34±0.9	-13.8

The decrease in properties can be attributed to the increase in weight loss/gain during ultraviolet and/or condensation in neat samples in comparison to nanophased samples. This enhancement and less degradation due to conditioning can also be attributed to better crosslinking, barrier properties of nanoclay in 2 wt.% samples.

Micrographic Analyses- Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Fiber/matrix interface region plays a crucial role in durability of composites in aqueous environment. The detrimental effects of fluid absorption under elevated temperatures on the matrix of the composites resulting in matrix cracking due to swelling, plasticization is of secondary importance when compared to the damage in the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix. The effects of moisture on both the tested and untested conditioned samples were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The speculation derived earlier for the enhancement in mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties with addition of small weight percentages of nanoclay (1-2 wt.%) is clear from these micrographs. Addition of nanoclay enhances the crosslinking between polymer chains and provides better chemical and interfacial bonding. Figure 5(a-b) shows the micrographs of neat and nanophased untested samples hot-wet conditioned at 80°C for 90 days. Weakening of the bonding is seen by higher resin separation from the fibers with increasing temperature. It is possible that water reaching the fiber–matrix interface softened or destroyed the adhesion between the two phases. Also the presence of moisture might have reduced the residual stresses between fiber and matrix generated during fabrication. The presence of elevated temperature adds to this degradation process by producing matrix cracks and interfacial cracking. This hypothesis becomes more evident from the micrographs of failed neat and nanophased samples conditioned similarly, i.e. hot-wet 80°C -90 days as shown in Fig. 5(c-d). No interfacial bonding was observed and the matrix was destroyed completely in neat tested samples. However 2 wt.% tested samples showed much better interfacial bonding evidence from thick layer of matrix on the surface of broken fibers as seen in Fig. 5(d).

Fig. 5(a-d). Flexural stress- strain response of ultraviolet radiation and/or condensation conditioned Samples.

As reported in Schutte [9], hydrolysis of the bisphenol-A epoxy resin by hot water is a form of chemical degradation of the matrix. When a resin is hydrolyzed, the ester bonds are destroyed. With less bonding between and within the polymer chains, the chains will slide past each other with greater ease; thus, inelastic deformation is achieved at smaller loads resulting loss of stiffness. In contrast, addition of nanoclay increases the crosslinking density and enhances the bonding as shown in Fig. 5d, thereby reducing the degradation in properties even at wet and elevated temperature conditions.

Figure 6 shows the scanning electron micrographs of unexposed and UV irradiated for 15 days samples. Small chunk of resin spalled from the surface. Surface erosion was observed in all the specimens irritated by UV radiation for 15 days as shown in Fig. 6. Such surface erosion could explain the weight loss of composite materials irritated by UV radiation and/or condensation resulting in degradation of properties.

Fig. 6. Scanning electron micrographs of (a) unexposed, (b) UV radiation exposed for 15 days samples.

CONCLUSION

It is shown here that E-glass epoxy fiber reinforced composites was sensitive to environmental conditioning especially under wet conditions. The weight gain was higher for all the wet conditions samples when exposed to elevated temperatures. Addition of 1-2 wt.% nanoclay decreased the weight gain. Mechanical properties were found to degrade with increase in time. 2 wt.% GFRP composites showed enhancement in properties in all the conditions over its neat counterpart. In some cases, samples subjected to hot-dry conditioned at 60°C showed increase in properties over room temperature conditioned samples. Decrease in properties was found for samples conditioned upto 15 days afterwards comparatively less degradation is found. Scanning electron micrographs revealed surface erosion and interfacial delamination in UV and elevated temperature wet conditioned samples. These micrographs provided clear evidence of the effects of nanoclay and moisture absorption. Enhancement in interfacial bonding was observed in 2 wt.% composite samples, both at room temperature and hot-wet conditioning.

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